

The 2024 Emergency Events Database Archive

The Year in Review and Historical Data Updates

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Abstract

The 2024 Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT) Archive (Version 2) extends the 2023 Archive (Version 1) to 2024, providing a retrospective analysis of the newly added year, with 604 disasters that caused 89,030 deaths, affected 168.59 million people, and generated US\$277.41 billion in losses. The new archive also enables direct comparison with the 2023 release (Version 1) to document the updates made in disaster impact reporting between the two releases. Key revisions include the addition of the 2024 European heatwave mortality estimate, which alone accounts for 62,557 deaths, and significant updates to economic loss figures for Hurricane Helene and seasonal floods in China. The archive also documents improvements in interoperability, with 1,504 new GLIDE identifiers, 878 HANZE linkages, and expanded USGS earthquake references, alongside the ongoing transition from GAUL 2015 to GADM 4.1 geocoding. These changes enhance the database's spatial precision and facilitate federated use of complementary disaster catalogs. The 2024 EM-DAT Archive, released under a CC-BY-NC-ND license and validated with the EM-TEST framework, is publicly available via the UCLouvain Dataverse. It serves as a FAIR-compliant foundation for open and reproducible disaster research, supporting retrospective reassessment and methodological advancements in disaster data towards improved risk understanding and reduction.

Keywords

Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT), International disaster database, Disaster epidemiology, Disaster human impact, Disaster economic impact, Natural hazards, Technological hazards

28 **Introduction**

29 Since 1988, the Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT) has compiled standardized information on
30 more than 27,000 disasters worldwide, triggered by natural and technological hazards from 1900
31 onward [1,2]. For each country-level event, it records key descriptors (hazard type, timing, location)
32 and impact metrics, including deaths, affected people and economic losses. Data are extracted and
33 validated from curated institutional, humanitarian, reinsurance, governmental, and press sources
34 [1]. EM-DAT is updated weekly and made available free of charge for non-commercial use through
35 the data portal (www.emdat.be), subject to registration and license terms that prevent redistribution.

36 Given the project's longevity and wide use (e.g., 40,000+ Google Scholar citations), periodic
37 archiving of EM-DAT and monitoring its evolution have become essential in many respects. Archiving
38 helps ensure that disaster loss data remain Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
39 (FAIR) [3], supports open and reproducible research, facilitates compliance with journal data
40 requirements, and allows readers to reassess findings based on earlier database versions. Over
41 time, successive FAIR archives also make it possible to track changes in the database's structure
42 and content.

43 The EM-DAT reference paper [1] described the database using the EM-DAT Archive Version 1 [4],
44 released in 2023 and covering 1900-2023. This Archive is distributed under a CC-BY-NC-ND
45 license [5], which permits redistribution, in line with open publication requirements. This data note
46 introduces the second archive [6], which extends coverage to 2024, and enables a retrospective
47 analysis of that year while highlighting the changes relative to the 2024 EM-DAT Annual Report [7]. By
48 directly comparing the two archived versions over their shared 1900-2023 records, we also quantify
49 the scale and nature of major historical updates in EM-DAT, and provide an empirical view of the
50 database's evolution. We discuss the implications of these revisions for data interpretation,
51 interoperability, and the limits of disaster impact reporting. The supplementary materials provide a
52 more detailed description of the data comparison.

53 **2024 Disaster Events Highlights**

54 The 2024 EM-DAT Archive records 604 disasters in 2024, causing 89,030 deaths, affecting 168.59
55 million people, and generating US\$277.41 billion in losses (2024 US\$). Of these, 430 were natural

56 hazards excluding biological ones,¹ and accounted for most of the impact, with 79,808 deaths
57 (89.6%), 168.1 million affected people (99.7%), and US\$277.41 billion in losses (100%), indicating
58 that no technological or biological events are recorded with documented economic losses.

59 To update the 2024 EM-DAT report, we present the top 10 tables on 2024 natural-hazard events
60 (Tables 1–3), with background references for additional context. Because disaster losses are
61 typically heavy-tailed, a small number of events often captures annual patterns well. Here, the top
62 10 events, 2.3% of registered natural-hazard events, account for 68.4% of total mortality, 57.2% of
63 the total number of affected people, and 68% of reported economic losses. EM-DAT estimates for
64 the total 2024 economic losses remain lower than those of global reinsurers, such as Munich Re,
65 Swiss Re, and AON, which range from US\$320 to US\$368 billion [8–10], reflecting differences
66 between system design, entry criteria, and data availability.

67 Overall, 2024 was dominated by extreme heat and Atlantic hurricanes: European heatwaves alone
68 caused an estimated 62,557 deaths across 31 countries — nearly four times the rest of the top-10
69 mortality events combined — while the US hurricane season (Helene, Milton, and Beryl) generated
70 US\$125 billion in losses, accounting for nearly half of the year's global total.

71 **Mortality Impact**

72 The 2024 Archive records 79,808 natural-hazard deaths, far above the 16,753 reported in the 2024
73 annual report [7]. This difference is driven almost entirely by the addition of the 2024 European
74 heatwave events, which were estimated to have caused more than 62,000 deaths across 31
75 countries (Table 1, #1), in a study published in September 2025 [11].

76 Other heatwaves also appear in the top 10 (Table 1). During the Hajj pilgrimage to Mecca in June
77 2024, 1,301 people died, according to the Saudi health minister [12], during an extreme heat event,
78 with temperatures reaching 51.8°C [13]. Several other Asian countries, including India (#5),
79 Bangladesh, Pakistan (#9), Cambodia, Laos, Thailand, Myanmar, Vietnam, and the Philippines, also
80 experienced severe and sustained heatwave exposure [14–16]. The mortality burden is likely
81 underestimated and not fully captured in EM-DAT (see Discussions). In the southwestern United

¹ Natural hazards, excluding biological ones (e.g., epidemics, infestations, or animal incidents) is the historical focus and reporting standard used in the EM-DAT annual report. Technological hazards are, therefore, not covered in the EM-DAT annual report series. Unless explicated otherwise, reference to natural hazard in this paper refers to “natural hazards, excluding biological ones.”

Table 1. Top 10 Natural-Hazard Disasters in EM-DAT by ‘Total Deaths’ in 2024

Rank	Country	Disaster Type or Name	Total Deaths	References
1	Europe (grouped) ¹	Heat wave	62,557*	[11]
2	Saudi Arabia	Hajj heat wave	1,301	[12,13]
3	Afghanistan	Severe winter conditions	1,197	[18]
4	USA	Heat wave	1,006	[17]
5	India	Heat wave	733	[14–16]
6	Japan	Noto Peninsula Earthquake	699*	[19–21]
7	Papua New Guinea	Enga Landslide	670	[22,23]
8	Chad	Flood	576	[24]
9	Pakistan	Heat wave	568	[14–16]
10	Myanmar	Typhoon Yagi (Enteng)	460	[25–28]

¹ The European Heat Wave event includes 31 events at the country level in EM-DAT, grouped for reporting purposes

* Substantial change from the 2024 EM-DAT report figures [7]

82 States of America (USA), heat waves in Arizona and Nevada (#4) were associated with 1,006 deaths,
83 based on reports limited to Phoenix and Las Vegas [17].

84 Other major high-mortality events in Asia included the Afghanistan cold wave (#3), which
85 combined snowfalls, blizzards, landslides, and floods and caused nearly 1,200 deaths [18]. The Noto
86 Peninsula Earthquake (Mw 7.5) struck the Ishikawa Prefecture, Japan, on January 1, 2024 [19,20], and
87 according to recent official estimates [21], caused 699 deaths (#6), 148 more than reported in the
88 EM-DAT 2024 annual report [7]. In Papua New Guinea, the Enga Province Landslide (#7) buried
89 Yambali village, resulting in 670 official deaths, although estimates range from 160 to more than
90 2,000 [22,23]. In early September, Typhoon Yagi (Enteng, in the Philippines) and associated floods
91 and landslides [25] caused the highest death toll in Myanmar, with 360 deaths and 100 missing
92 persons (#10) [26]. The storm caused heavy losses in nearby countries, including Vietnam, where 345
93 people died, mainly in landslides [27].

94 In Africa, severe floods in Chad (#8) submerged large areas, destroying homes, infrastructure, and
95 farmland, and displacing thousands of people. The floods worsened food insecurity, disrupted
96 access to clean water and sanitation, and increased the risk of waterborne diseases. More than a
97 year later, many affected communities still required humanitarian assistance [24].

98 EM-DAT also records four major cholera outbreaks, classified as biological hazards, under post-
99 flood conditions: South Sudan (1,567 deaths), Sudan (1,508 deaths), Angola (759 deaths), and
100 Yemen (680 deaths) [29–32]. These outbreaks formed part of a broader regional resurgence that
101 threatens progress toward the 2030 global cholera elimination targets [33].

Table 2. Top 10 Natural-Hazard Disasters in EM-DAT by ‘Total Affected’ in 2024

Rank	Country	Disaster type or Name	Total Affected <i>millions</i>	References
1	Bangladesh	Heat Wave	33.0	[34]
2	Zambia	Drought	9.8	[40–43]
3	Philippines	Typhoon Trami (Kristine)	9.7	[44,45]
4	India	Flood (August)	8.0	[37–39]
5	Zimbabwe	Drought	7.6	[40–43]
6	Philippines	Typhoon Gaemi (Carina), Butchoy (Prapiroon)	6.5	[28,46,47]
7	Malawi	Drought	6.1	[40–43]
8	Bangladesh	Flood (August)	5.8	[37–39]
9	Bangladesh	Flood (June-July)	5.1	[37–39]
10	Bangladesh	Tropical cyclone Remal	4.6	[35]

102 Affected People

103 Compared with the 2024 annual report [7], the top 10 ranking by total affected people is unchanged
 104 (Table 2). Bangladesh ranks first, with 33 million people affected (Table 2, #1). This figure corresponds
 105 to children temporarily deprived of schooling during an unprecedented 24-day heatwave in April [34].
 106 One month later, Cyclone Remal struck Bangladesh on 26 May, severely affecting coastal areas [35]
 107 and 4.6 million people [36]. From late May to September, India and Bangladesh were also hit by
 108 severe monsoon floods, with a total of 18.9 million people affected across events #4, #8, and #9 [37–
 109 39]. In Bangladesh, the late-August floods (#8) evolved into a humanitarian crisis that was still
 110 ongoing in 2026 [37].

111 The 2024 tropical cyclone season was especially active in Southeast Asia [28,46]. In the
 112 Philippines, several major events entered the top 10 [44], notably Typhoon Trami (#3, locally named
 113 Kristine), Typhoon Gaemi (Carina), and Tropical Cyclone Prapiroon (Butchoy) (#6). Trami, which
 114 struck in October, affected about 9.7 million people and caused widespread flooding, displacement,
 115 and urgent needs in water, sanitation, food, and protection, particularly in already vulnerable areas
 116 [44,45]. In July, Gaemi and Prapiroon, combined with the southwest monsoon, affected more than
 117 6.5 million people. Gaemi alone brought record rainfall and flooding to Metro Manila and surrounding
 118 areas, prompting a state of calamity, and contributed to a combined death toll of 53 deaths
 119 [28,46,47].

120 By contrast, severe El Niño-induced droughts devastated parts of Southern Africa [40], leaving
 121 about 9.8 million people in Zambia (#2), 7.6 million in Zimbabwe (#5), and 6.1 million in Malawi (#7)
 122 facing acute food and water shortages [41–43].

123 **Economic Losses**

124 Table 3 lists the top 10 events by reported economic losses. Although global reinsurance estimates
 125 of total damage are generally higher than EM-DAT totals [8–10], the figures for the costliest events are
 126 broadly consistent, as reinsurance reports are also a priority source in EM-DAT [1]. Relative to the
 127 2024 annual report [7], two notable updates concern Hurricane Helene and the Chinese seasonal
 128 floods.

129 In 2024, about 47% of the US\$277.41 billion in losses reported by EM-DAT came from the US
 130 hurricane season. Three US events entered the top 10: Hurricane Beryl (#6, July), Hurricane Helene
 131 (#1, September), and Hurricane Milton (#2, October), totaling US\$125.2 billion in damage. Compared
 132 with the EM-DAT 2024 report, the estimate for Hurricane Helene increased from US\$56 billion—as
 133 initially reported in Munich Re’s annual report [9]—to US\$80 billion, a figure later cited by Munich Re
 134 [48]. The revised amount is also close to the US\$75 billion reported by AON [8], for losses including
 135 Mexico and Cuba, and to the US\$78.7 billion reported by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric
 136 Administration (NOAA) [49].

137 Reinsurance reports also identify Typhoon Yagi as one of the costliest cyclones of the year [8,9],
 138 with losses estimated at US\$12.9–14 billion. However, those losses were distributed across China,
 139 Vietnam, Thailand, Myanmar, the Philippines, and Laos and therefore did not place the event in the
 140 country-level top 10 (Table 3).

141 Another change from the 2024 annual report [7] is the inclusion of the seasonal floods in China (#4,
 142 Table 3). Estimating flood losses in China is difficult because flooding was widespread and recurrent

Table 3. Top 10 Natural-Hazard Disasters in EM-DAT by ‘Total Damage’ in 2024

Rank	Country	Disaster Type or Name	Total Damage <i>US\$ billion</i>	References
1	USA	Hurricane Helene	80.0*	[8,9,48,49]
2	USA	Hurricane Milton	38.0	[8,9,48,49]
3	Japan	Earthquake	15.0	[19–21]
4	China	Flood (June-July)	12.0*	[8,9,50,51]
5	Spain	Flood	11.0	[52,53]
6	USA	Hurricane Beryl	7.2	[8,9,48,49]
7	Brazil	Flood	7.0	[8,54]
8	USA	Storm (May)	6.6	[49,55]
9	Brazil	Drought	6.0	[8,50,56–58]
10	USA	Storm (March)	5.9	[49,59]

* Substantial change from the 2024 EM-DAT report figures [7]

143 from April through September, with the later part overlapping the typhoon season. The value reported
144 in Table 3 refers to June–July flooding and is consistent with reinsurance estimates of US\$12–16
145 billion [8,9], although Gallagher reports US\$31 billion for the full summer season [50]. According to
146 the National Disaster Reduction Center of China and the Ministry of Emergency Management, natural
147 hazards caused US\$55.87 billion in damage in 2024, with floods accounting for 64.8% and typhoons
148 for 21.3% [51].

149 The USA also experienced other major weather-related losses earlier in the year [49], with two
150 additional events appearing in the top 10. In March (#10), severe storms affected the central and
151 southern USA, bringing heavy rain, strong winds, tornadoes, and destructive hail [55]. From 6 to 10
152 May (#8), a major tornado outbreak swept across the central, southern, and southeastern states,
153 producing more than 165 tornadoes — including a devastating event in Oklahoma — and causing
154 US\$6.6 billion in damage [59].

155 Outside the USA, the Noto Peninsula earthquake ranks third in Table 3, with total losses of US\$15
156 billion [19–21]. In Spain, the Valencia DANA floods of late October and early November [52,53] were
157 among the ten costliest disasters worldwide in 2024, with losses estimated at US\$11–16 billion [8,9].
158 In April–May, floods in Rio Grande do Sul, southern Brazil, caused record damage, with estimates
159 ranging from US\$5 to US\$18 billion depending on the source, accounting method, and exchange rate
160 [8,54]. A joint report by the Inter-American Development Bank, the World Bank, and ECLAC provides
161 the most comprehensive estimate, placing direct material losses at roughly US\$7–8 billion (aligned
162 with Table 3) and indirect economic effects at about US\$9 billion [54].

163 These floods in Brazil contrast with the severe compound drought, heatwave, and fire conditions
164 observed across the Amazon during 2023-2024 [56,57]. Those conditions affected 59% of Brazil's
165 territory, and generated cascading impacts on water access, health, food security, and livelihoods
166 [58], with losses reported at around US\$6 billion [8,50]. With the addition of the seasonal floods in
167 China, the widespread drought across the southern, eastern, and northwestern USA dropped out of
168 the EM-DAT top 10 [7]. That drought was especially severe in Texas and persisted throughout the year,
169 peaking in summer and intensifying again in autumn and winter. It caused major agricultural losses
170 in several states, estimated at US\$5.4 billion [49]. According to the American Farm Bureau
171 Federation, drought- and heat-related crop losses in the USA totaled US\$11 billion in 2024 [60].

172 **Historical Revisions (1900–2023)**

173 A comparison of the unique ‘DisNo.’ identifiers shows that 150 entries were withdrawn and 124 were
 174 added. These changes may reflect newly identified events, the withdrawal of events that no longer
 175 meet the inclusion criteria, or the integration of new sources. In many cases, however, events were
 176 not simply added or removed but restructured at a finer or coarser resolution to match the reporting
 177 framework of the source considered most accurate or up to date. Such splitting and merging can
 178 require new ‘Dis No.’ identifiers.

179 Based on the ‘Last Update’ fields, 8,996 entries were manually edited between the 2023 and 2024
 180 archives over the shared 1900–2023 period. The most frequently edited field was ‘External IDs’, with
 181 2,372 edits, followed by ‘Location’, with 571 edits. These updates reflect efforts to improve EM-DAT
 182 interoperability and substantial work on disaster geocoding. These improvements are discussed
 183 below, along with the most important changes in the impact figures; more detailed figures are
 184 available in the supplementary materials.

185 **Improvements of Interoperability**

186 References to disaster event identifiers in external catalogs (‘External IDs’ in EM-DAT) have increased
 187 between the two archives (Table 4). The most significant increase is relative to the Global Unique
 188 Disaster Identifier Number (GLIDE), which is a unique, standardized identifier assigned to disaster
 189 events that enables unambiguous cross-referencing and data linkage across different disaster
 190 information systems [1,61]. The 1,504 additional GLIDE references primarily result from a reanalysis
 191 of existing assignments using machine-learning suggestions, which were then reviewed by two
 192 human operators [62].

193 The second most significant update concerns historical European floods and a newly introduced
 194 pairing of EM-DAT events with those found in the Historical Analysis of Natural Hazards in Europe
 195 (HANZE) [63]. The HANZE ID assignments were performed manually by a single operator, who

Table 4. Updates in the ‘External IDs’ Column Between the 2023 and 2024 Archives

External ID Label	Catalog Full Name	2023	2024	Diff.
DFO	Dartmouth Flood Observatory	294	296	+2
GLIDE	GLobal Unique Disaster IDentifier Number	1,832	3,336	+1,504
USGS ComCat	USGS ANSS Comprehensive Earthquake Catalog	425	544	+119
HANZE	Historical Analysis of Natural Hazards in Europe	0	878	+878

196 reviewed the HANZE catalog. The focus remained on event pairing rather than a systematic review of
197 impact figures. The pairing enables explicit links between the two catalogs to compare impact figures
198 and to exploit HANZE's higher administrative resolution at the third level of the Nomenclature of
199 Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS3).

200 Lastly, most identifiers pointing to the US Geological Survey (USGS) Earthquake Catalog were
201 added based on a prior mapping conducted for loss-model development [64]. This linkage enables
202 users to query seismological data and ShakeMaps for earthquake events in EM-DAT.

203 **New Geocoding Reference**

204 Until 2025, EM-DAT used the FAO's Global Administrative Unit Layers (GAUL 2015) to geocode
205 disaster events at the sub-national level (up to Admin-2). Since 2014, natural-hazard disasters,
206 excluding biological ones, have been geocoded in EM-DAT, with retrospective work starting in 2000.

207 From 2026 onwards, the outdated GAUL reference was replaced by GADM 4.1 (Database of Global
208 Administrative Areas). The transition relied on an automated migration procedure in which GAUL and
209 GADM geometries were compared using overlap and proximity indicators — primarily the Jaccard
210 index and the Hausdorff distance — to identify the best-matching GADM unit(s) for each GAUL entry.
211 Where no satisfactory match was found, a fallback strategy assigned the nearest parent
212 administrative unit, at the cost of some spatial precision.

213 As of April 2026, approximately 90% of GAUL footprints had been successfully migrated. In
214 practice, the 'Admin Units' column containing GAUL identifiers remains in the Archive to avoid
215 introducing breaking changes without a deprecation period, while a new 'GADM Admin Units' column
216 has been introduced. Figure 1 provides a breakdown of completion status by year for GAUL and
217 GADM units. Because GAUL geocoding was not systematic in recent years, especially for the latest
218 years under review, the remaining backlog in GADM geocoding will need to be cleared manually in
219 the coming months. More comprehensive or alternative sub-national geocoding coverage can be
220 found in the literature [65–67].

Figure 1. Subnational Geocoding Completion by Year for GAUL 2015 and GADM 4.1 Administrative Units. Bars show the percentage of disaster events geocoded at the sub-national level under the legacy GAUL 2015 framework (blue) and the replacement GADM 4.1 framework (red). Annotations report the total number of geocodable events per year (n). Only natural-hazard disasters excluding biological events are considered; GADM coverage reflects the automated migration procedure described in the text, with residual unmatched entries assigned to the nearest parent unit or flagged for manual geocoding.

221 **Impact Figure Updates**

222 In Figure 2, we summarize the most significant changes in the EM-DAT impact figures between the
 223 two archives by examining absolute and relative shifts in annual totals. More detailed breakdowns
 224 are provided in the supplementary materials. In general, the largest changes were introduced during
 225 the 1900–1965 period, excluding years influenced by World Wars I and II, and in the last decade,
 226 reflecting source availability for impact review. Most historical updates resulted from the reanalysis
 227 of other catalogs, primarily HANZE [62] for European floods and Wikimpacts [68], a global catalog of
 228 climate-related disasters extracted from Wikipedia, or from recalled disasters brought back to
 229 attention by recent disasters or commemoration events.

230 The most important changes in reported ‘Total Deaths’ relate to the 1934 Bihar-Nepal earthquake
 231 in Nepal and India [69], a major event that was initially excluded from EM-DAT because of insufficient
 232 source material. The event, which resulted in 8,519 deaths in Nepal and 7,188 additional deaths in
 233 Bihar, India [69], was reconsidered in the context of the 10-year anniversary of the 2015 Gorkha
 234 earthquake. Likewise, the 2025 magnitude-8.8 Kamchatka earthquake (July 30) brought renewed
 235 attention to a historical earthquake in the same region: the 1952 Severo-Kurilsk earthquake and
 236 tsunami. The latter was revised from 0 to 2,336 deaths, aligning with the lower bound reported by
 237 Wikipedia sources [70]. In addition, the death toll of Typhoon Wanda (1956) in China was increased
 238 from 2,000 to 4,935, also based on Wikipedia figures [68,71]. Finally, the 1930 San Zenón hurricane

Figure 2. Year-by-year impact differences between two EM-DAT database releases (1900–2023). Each row represents one impact metric: total deaths, total persons affected, and total damage in nominal US\$. Top panel — absolute differences, normalized independently per metric to $[-1, 1]$; Right-aligned gray labels report the actual maximum absolute difference used for normalization. Bottom panel — relative differences expressed as percentage change relative to the earlier release, clipped at $\pm 500\%$. Color scale: blue, new release reports lower values; red, new release reports higher values; white, no change.

239 [72] had been encoded twice, with 2,000 deaths reported for the Dominican Republic—the correct
 240 country—and once for Dominica, an error corrected in the 2024 Archive.

241 Regarding the number of affected people, the most significant change again concerns Typhoon
 242 Wanda (1956), which rose from no recorded value to 11 million [68,71]. Other changes are at least an
 243 order of magnitude lower; however, they remain relatively important (Figure 2) because less
 244 information is available for earlier periods. For instance, only five people were reported as affected
 245 by disasters in 1934 in the 2023 Archive, making the addition of 15,000 affected people for the 1934
 246 hurricane season in the USA an important relative change.

247 Relative changes in economic losses may also be high in historical periods for the same reason.
 248 Nonetheless, the largest relative change concerns the Pittsburgh flood of 1936 [73], with an added
 249 US\$200 million, equivalent to US\$4.51 billion in 2024 prices. In absolute terms, the most important
 250 change in economic losses is the removal of double counting for the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake
 251 sequence in Japan, recorded in EM-DAT as two events in close temporal proximity, resulting in a
 252 downward revision of US\$38 billion.

253 **Discussion**

254 The 2024 EM-DAT Archive documents several revisions relative to the 2024 annual report [7],
255 reflecting data updates made after the report's publication. The most consequential is the near-
256 fivefold increase in total natural-hazard deaths, driven almost entirely by the addition of the European
257 heatwave mortality estimate published in September 2025 [11], more than nine months after the
258 disaster year closed. Economic losses for Hurricane Helene and the inclusion of seasonal floods in
259 China were also revised substantially. Together, these examples illustrate a central challenge in
260 disaster-impact reporting: some disasters are initially documented using provisional “hot” figures,
261 reported during or immediately after the emergency phase, whereas more comprehensive impact
262 reports or reanalyses may only become available months or years later.

263 This delay is especially clear for heat-related mortality. Unlike sudden-onset hazards, heat-
264 related deaths are rarely observable in real time and typically require method- or data-sensitive
265 estimates derived from excess-mortality or exposure-response epidemiological analyses published
266 in scientific journals, such as the sources recently used in EM-DAT [11,74,75]. These studies are
267 currently limited to the past few years and to European countries. Accordingly, while EM-DAT
268 heatwave-related figure availability is increasing, related biases are also becoming more apparent.
269 Overall, 50.37% of heatwave mortality in EM-DAT is reported in the last three years of the 2024
270 archive; 91.44% of heatwave-related deaths are recorded in Europe, and no number is available for
271 Africa [76].

272 Moreover, while these studies provide a more consistent framework, they report mortality figures
273 for the whole summer period, which does not align neatly with the EM-DAT definition of disasters as
274 emergency situations, nor with impact-based early warning systems [77]. This mismatch may inflate
275 reported totals, alongside other factors such as reporting that increasingly focuses on more detailed
276 population subgroups.

277 We are currently in a transitional period for evaluation and reporting of heat-related deaths, and
278 EM-DAT heatwave impact figures will likely be revised again, as more EM-DAT or DRR-aligned
279 frameworks are proposed. By design, EM-DAT reports disasters based on published materials. Yet,
280 the main limitation for heatwave mortality remains the global lack of available or accessible mortality
281 data [78], which constrains the epidemiological evaluation of heatwave-related deaths.

282 The 2024 Archive also reflects targeted efforts to improve EM-DAT's interoperability and spatial
283 precision. The addition of 1,504 GLIDE references [61,62], 878 HANZE linkages [63], and expanded

284 USGS earthquake identifiers [64] enables users to augment EM-DAT records with hazard, exposure,
285 or impact data from complementary catalogs without re-ingesting those sources—a federated
286 approach that respects data ownership while broadening analytical reach. On the geocoding side,
287 the ongoing transition from GAUL 2015 to GADM 4.1, approximately 90% complete as of April 2026,
288 provides a more current and openly maintained spatial reference, which is essential for joining EM-
289 DAT records to population or exposure datasets in risk analysis.

290 Finally, the historical revisions documented between the 2023 and 2024 archives position EM-DAT
291 as an evolving knowledge base that continues to improve while also making its current limitations
292 more visible. These revisions further demonstrate the scientific value of openly published catalogs
293 such as HANZE [63] and Wikimpacts [68] as sources for systematic EM-DAT reanalysis.
294 Complementarily, historical disaster events, such as the 1934 Bihar–Nepal earthquake and the 1952
295 Severo-Kurilsk earthquake, were revised or newly incorporated following renewed attention during
296 recent or anniversary events, supported by the increasing availability of digitized sources. More
297 broadly, FAIR and open data products—including the EM-DAT Archive itself—provide a traceable
298 foundation on which the scientific community can both contribute to and build upon EM-DAT,
299 supporting reproducible disaster research without dependence on the live, access-controlled
300 database.

301 **Data, Software, & Code Availability**

302 The 2023 and 2024 EM-DAT archives are accessible through the UCLouvain Dataverse [4,6]. The archive is
303 technically validated with the EM-TEST framework [79] before publication. Tables and figures were generated
304 in Python, using matplotlib and pandas [80,81]. Differences between the two archives were computed with the
305 pandas ‘compare’ method.

306 **CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement**

307 DD: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal
308 analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. VW: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Data curation.
309 RB: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. AA: Writing –
310 review & editing. NS: Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

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315 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

316 None declared.

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